

Structural Field Testing and Evaluation of Two Demonstration FRP Deck Bridges: Case Studies on FRP Panel Deck Bridge and Temporary Bypass Bridge

Original Submission Date: July 31, 2008

Revised Submission Date: November 14, 2008

Paper No. 09-2503

Word Count: 7,209

Yoon-Si Lee

West Virginia University Institute of Technology

405 Fayette Pike

Montgomery, WV 25136

304-442-3370

Fax 304-442-3391

Yoon-Si.Lee@mail.wvu.edu

Travis Hosteng

Iowa State University – Bridge Engineering Center

2711 S. Loop Dr., Suite 4700

Ames, IA 50010

515-294-7197

Fax 515-294-0467

kickhos@iastate.edu

Ursula Deza

Iowa State University – Bridge Engineering Center

2711 S. Loop Dr., Suite 4700

Ames, IA 50010

515-294-8103

Fax 515-294-0467

udeza@iastate.edu

James S. Nelson

Iowa Department of Transportation – Office of Bridges and Structures

800 Lincoln Way

Ames, IA 50010

515-233-7723

Fax 515-239-1978

James.S.Nelson@dot.iowa.gov

Terry Wipf (corresponding author)

Iowa State University – Bridge Engineering Center

2711 S. Loop Dr., Suite 4700

Ames, IA 50010

515-294-6979

Fax 515-294-0467

tjwipf@iastate.edu

Brent Phares
Iowa State University – Bridge Engineering Center
2711 S. Loop Dr., Suite 4700
Ames, IA 50010
515-294-5879
Fax 515-294-0467
bphares@iastate.edu

Doug Wood
Iowa State University – Civil, Construction and Environmental Engineering Department
Town Engineering Building
Ames, IA 50010
515-294-3768
Fax 515-294-8216
dwoody@iastate.edu

F. Wayne Klaiber
Iowa State University – Bridge Engineering Center
2711 S. Loop Dr., Suite 4700
Ames, IA 50010
515-294-8763
Fax 515-294-0467
klaiber@iastate.edu

ABSTRACT

In the last decade, the use of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites technology has emerged as an option in structural engineering and has shown its potential for structural applications in bridges. FRP composite materials are appealing in that they are highly resistant to corrosion, have a low weight, and have a high tensile strength. This paper summarizes two projects, funded through the Federal Highway Administration's Innovative Bridge Research and Construction program, that investigate the applicability and effectiveness of using FRP composites in bridge construction: (1) Bettendorf FRP panel deck bridge, the first FRP bridge deck in the US that uses composite action with prestressed concrete girders, and (2) FRP temporary bypass bridge, developed to replace existing steel temporary bridges. The paper presents structural field performance results for each demonstration project and for each bridge provides correlation of the performance with design parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) has gained increasing interest among the bridge engineering community due to its outstanding mechanical characteristics and non-corrosive nature. These unique FRP characteristics eliminate the maintenance problems caused by moisture, salt air, and termites that pose concerns for typical bridges constructed in concrete, steel and wood. In addition, FRP has approximately 10 times higher tensile strength capacity than mild grade steel and its strength is governed by its ability to sustain a load without excessive deformation or failure. It should be noted that for sustained loads, that creep rupture behavior of FRP is less desirable than that for steel. Its high strength-to-weight ratio is of true benefit since its dead load contribution is minimal and, thereby, allowing a member composed of FRP to support relatively larger live loads.

In the recent past, the use of FRP composites technology has been adopted by many bridge agencies nationwide and has shown its potential for structural applications in bridges [1, 2]. The increased use of composite materials is in large part due to the Federal Highway Administration's (FHWA) Innovative Bridge Research and Construction (IBRC) program, which promotes and reinforces the use of innovative materials, construction techniques, and structures in general. Through support of the IBRC program, the Iowa DOT has initiated numerous projects to investigate the effectiveness and applicability of using FRP composite materials in strengthening, repairing, as well as new construction of bridges. New York State in particular has been active in the implementation and evaluation of FRP bridges, and several reports provide documented construction and structural performance evaluations through load testing [3, 4]. This paper documents two projects that evaluate the applicability of FRP decks in bridge construction.

BETTENDORF FRP PANEL DECK BRIDGE [5]

The objective of this study was to evaluate the structural performance of a three span bridge, one span of which was constructed with FRP deck panels, that carries the 53rd Avenue extension over Crow Creek in Bettendorf, Iowa (Figure 1). It is the first FRP bridge deck in the US that uses composite action with prestressed concrete girders and, at the time of the construction, was also the widest FRP deck (98 ft – 8 in.). Field monitoring was performed on the subject bridge to assess the performance of the FRP panel deck under actual bridge loading. Instrumentation was placed at important locations to collect displacement and strain data. The testing program consisted of two short-term tests and long-term monitoring of the bridge. The test results are compared, where applicable, with measured conventional-deck field behavior and empirical design assumptions.

Bridge Description

The bridge is 173 ft-7.5 in. long, 98 ft-8 in. wide and consists of three different deck material combinations that are supported by prestressed concrete (PC) girders. The west and middle span decks were continuously constructed with cast-in-place concrete reinforced with epoxy coated steel and glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) bars, respectively, while the east bridge deck was constructed with a total of 12 DuraSpan® 766 pultruded FRP panels (thickness equivalent to 7.66 in. as shown in Figures 2a and 2b. Two 4-in. deep holes were pre-drilled every 24 in. on the top flange of the C14MS PC girders to hold 3/4-in. u-shape shear stirrups fixed with a two-part epoxy (Figure 2c). Between the panels and the girders, two polystyrene supports were attached with adhesive to form the haunch (varying from approximately 1 in. to 2 in. thick). The

panels were interconnected by three 6-in. wide FRP splices on the top. The FRP deck holes were filled with non-shrink grout to create composite action. To attach the concrete barrier rail to the FRP deck, stirrups were anchored in the deck with non-shrink grout (Figure 2d). The barrier railing on the FRP deck span was constructed separately from the rest of the rail system to ensure thermal compatibility. The bridge was opened to traffic in May 2003.

Figure 1. Photographs of Bettendorf Bridge.

Figure 2. Typical FRP deck panel and prestressed concrete girder.

Short-Term Monitoring

The short-term testing consisted of monitoring the bridge behavior under controlled live loading. Strain data were obtained from the top and bottom flange of twelve girders in the FRP-deck span, and six girders in the reinforced concrete (RC) span as well as one FRP panel instrumented with four strain gages (Figures 3a through 3c). During the testing, the bridge was loaded by driving a loaded tandem axle dump truck with a total weight of 67.4 kips in 2003 (rear axle of 50.0 kips) and 65.9 kips in 2004 (real axle of 48.9 kips). This truck crossed the bridge at crawl speed in six transverse paths (Figures 3d and 3e) which were selected to either produce maximum response levels or represent typical traffic patterns.

Figure 3. Overall instrumentation and load truck location detail.

By reviewing the recorded strains (Figure 4), it was determined that there were no significant changes in strain levels between the two tests that were separated by approximately one year. Note that the results were normalized based on the gross vehicle weight and rear axle differences (1.02) to account for the difference in truck loading between the two tests. In some

(a) Girder B

(b) Girder C

Figure 4. Strain response comparison near mid span – Path Y1

cases there were slightly lower readings in the second year. Note that the strain data in the FRP-deck span showed noticeable spikes in the top flange data, which can be attributed to the lower stiffness of the FRP composite deck as compared to the concrete deck. In general, based on the data collected, there was no significant loss of stiffness in the FRP-deck span during the two-year monitoring period. As illustrated by the collected data, the FRP-deck span exhibited almost no continuity with the adjacent span, while the RC deck span appeared to be fully continuous with the adjacent span. This may have a significant influence on the moments induced in each span (i.e., this infers that the positive region moments of the FRP-deck span will not be reduced due to continuity as would the RC deck span in the positive region moments). When comparing both spans, it is observed that the girder strains were larger in the FRP-deck span than in the RC-deck span. The higher strain levels in the FRP span are primarily attributed to the much lower stiffness of the composite FRP deck/girder section (the approximate cross section EI values, respectively, for the FRP span and the RC span are $EI_{\text{FRP-PC girder}} = 581,139,000 \text{ kip-in}^2$ and $EI_{\text{RC-PC girder}} = 1,362,300,000 \text{ kip-in}^2$).

The load distribution coefficients (LDCs) were calculated using the measured bottom flange girder strains. As expected, the most critical loading condition occurred when the truck was driven close to the barrier. The resulting maximum LDC in the FRP-deck span was 47% in 2003, and 43% in 2004 (Figure 5a). For the same loading, the LDC in the RC deck span was 43% in 2003, and 41% in 2004. The obtained data indicated that the RC-deck span was more effective in laterally distributing the loading than the FRP-deck span. The AASHTO Standard Specification [6] provides distribution factors (LDFs) in terms of truck percentage while the AASHTO LRFD Specifications [7] defines the LDFs to be calculated based on the mechanical and materialistic properties of the composite section. In the absence of code specifications for FRP panel decks, it should be noted that the design was strength based. Figure 5b presents the LDCs for two lanes computed by superimposing multiple passes of the test truck. The LDC per girder was calculated as a percentage of the superposition of bottom strains and assuming the linear elastic response of the bridge superstructure. As can be seen, the test LDCs were below the AASHTO values and no significant change was observed during the two-year monitoring period.

In order to evaluate the deck-to-girder connectivity, the neutral axis of the composite section was computed based on the gage locations and field collected strain data and compared with theoretical calculations of the neutral axis location (provided by the designer), assuming full composite action. The results indicated that the central girders were resisting a notable level of torsional forces that were neglected in the original design. Figure 6 presents the results of the neutral axis location for Path Y1 measured from the bottom flange over the most heavily loaded girders. In general, it appears that the neutral axis locations did not significantly change over time and that the central girders may not have achieved full composite action with the FRP deck panels. While the composite actions for the Girders B and C appear to be likely achieved, the measured neutral axis location for Girder D was below the non-composite action (19.5 in.). This can likely be attributed to a weak shear connection and the possibility of torsion effects of the truck loading typically ignored during design. Despite these findings, the measured strain levels were below the design values, thereby, giving assurance that the torsional effects and partial composite action may not be significantly impacting the strength of the prestressed girders.

(a) Comparison of FRP and RC deck – Path Y1

(b) LDCs superposition – Path Y5 and Y6

Figure 5. Load distribution coefficient comparison.

Figure 6. Neutral axis of FRP deck span – Path Y1.

Findings

The following conclusions and observations are drawn from the field monitoring, analysis and field inspection:

- The FRP panels appear to behave elastically.
- The PC girder strains levels remained similar over the test period. Variations in strain over time indicate that there had been no decline in flexural stiffness.
- The LDCs from field tests were less than the AASHTO Specification (Standard and LRFD) LDC values and indicated no significant change from 2003 to 2004.
- In general, it was observed that some intermediate girders may not have fully attained composite action with the FRP deck. However, the strain levels measured were below the design strains.
- After one year of service, there were signs of deck overlay cracking in the transverse direction to the traffic, but the cracking had no effect on the structural performance of the bridge. The cracks aligned with the edges of the FRP tube components that comprise the panels. Maintenance to the overlay was performed by the bridge owner.
- No damage to the girders was observed.

IOWA DOT FRP TEMPORARY BYPASS BRIDGE [8]

Due to the deteriorating condition of existing steel temporary bridges (Figure 7a), the Iowa DOT initiated a research project to determine if a FRP deck bridge could be a suitable replacement for the steel temporary bridges. The replacement system is approximately 35 percent lighter than the steel alternative, potentially easier to transport, and the few components that may deteriorate are readily replaceable. This new FRP deck bridge for temporary bypass applications consists of two 39 ft-10 in. by 13 ft-6 ½ in. deck panels, measuring approximately 3 ft in thickness, that are spliced with steel plates along the centerline of the roadway to form a bridge that spans 39 ft-0 in. with a roadway width of 24 ft-0 in. (from face of one barrier rail to that of opposite side barrier rail) for two 12 ft-0 in. traffic lanes (Figure 7b). Brief summaries of the design,

fabrication and evaluation of the FRP deck bridge for temporary bypass applications are followed.

Figure 7. Steel and FRP deck temporary bypass bridges.

Design

The design of the FRP deck bridge was a proprietary design by Hardcore Composites that was verified by HNTB Corporation. The design was based on an allowable stress analysis and elastic deflection limits. Final design calculations were completed by Hardcore Composites, and checked by engineers at the Iowa DOT and Iowa State University. The FRP deck bridge is assumed to behave on a quasi-isotropic basis for calculating moments and shears due to dead load and live load. Design load stresses due to live load were based on the AASHTO HS20 loading. The Factor of Safety (FS) used for the allowable stress was $FS=5$ in accordance with the current recommended practices from the FHWA [9]. The railing connection is designed to satisfy Test Level Two (TL-2) requirements. Deflection limits were per the AASHTO Standard Specification $L/800$ allowable deflection criteria. The assumed clear span was 39 ft-0 in. leading to a 0.59 in. deflection limit. Deflection calculations were based on an AASHTO H20 loading that yielded a deflection of 0.473 in. satisfying the allowable deflection criteria. The bridge traffic barrier rail is designed for Test Level Two (TL-2) in accordance with NCHRP Report 350 “Recommended Procedures for the Safety Performance Evaluation of Highway Features” [10]. According to ASHTO LRFD Bridge Design Specifications [11] TL-2 is generally acceptable for work zones and most local and collector roads with favorable site conditions as well as where a small number of heavy vehicles is expected and posted speeds are reduced.

Fabrication and Construction

Each panel is composed of seven layers, called plies, of QM6408 FRP fabric on the bottom and top and 3 plies on each vertical side. These layers of FRP are what provide the resistance to bending stresses in the structure. The core of each panel is composed of 600 8 in. x 16 in. x 36 in. foam ‘bottles’ individually wrapped with one ply of TV3400 FRP fabric, and as a whole provide the shear resistance for the structure. Once all the bottles are installed and wrapped with FRP plies, vinyl ester resin was infused into the structure through a process called Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM). Presented in Figure 8 are various stages of fabrication of the FRP panels. Prior to the delivery, the FRP deck panels were painted for protection of the FRP material from ultraviolet (UV) degradation and the top of the deck was coated with the epoxy and aggregate wearing surface. When the bridge traffic barrier rail is not

attached both panels can be shipped on a flatbed trailer as an oversized legal load (Figure 9a). The panels are lifted off the trailer using a small crane as shown in Figure 9b. At calculated locations, eight foam bottles in each panel were replaced with bottles outfitted with the lifting hardware that consists of an anchored steel plate with a threaded hole to accept bolt-on D-rings.

(a) Installation of bottom FRP plies

(b) Bottles

(c) Elevation view of panel

(d) End view of panel

Figure 8. Installation of bottom FRP piles and FRP wrapped foam bottles.

Figure 9. Temporary FRP Bridge delivery and installed traffic barrier rail.

The FRP Deck panels were set on the temporary abutments that are comprised of wide flange steel beams to allow for the installation of the steel splice plates and testing of the panels. Splicing the two FRP deck sections together was accomplished by using a series of steel plates with rods welded to them. The connection was then completed by bolting bottom splice plates to the rods. Once the splice plates are installed, the riding surface is complete for traffic, which was followed by installing the bridge traffic barrier railing. The wearing surface of the deck panels consists of a 3/8 in. layer of abrasive epoxy covering the entire deck surface except the areas occupied by connection plates. The barrier rail is bolted through the deck in a similar fashion as the splice plates (Figure 9c and 9d). The only difference is that the rods are threaded at both ends and secured with nuts instead of welding. Note that the temporary detour bridge can be transported with or without the bridge traffic barrier railing installed. The signed speed for the temporary detour will be 35 mph.

Testing and Evaluation

A load testing was performed in November, 2005 using a fully loaded Iowa DOT tandem axle truck with axle weights of 11.9 kip, 16.1 kip and 16.3 kip spaced at 17 ft-6 in. and 4 ft-6 in. The two segments of the bridge were joined together with the center splice plates prior to loading.

The truck was statically placed on the structure in three load positions and, in all cases, was positioned longitudinally, facing north, to induce the maximum moment in the bridge. Figure 10 illustrates the transverse load positioning of the truck (LC1, LC2 and LC3) and test data collection instrumentation.

Figure 10. Instrumentation and truck positioning.

Figures 11 illustrate the transverse distribution of strain at mid-span for a single lane loaded and two lanes loaded, respectively. The two lanes loaded case was approximated by superposition of LC 1 and 3. As shown, it is evident that the distribution of strain is relatively symmetric about the longitudinal centerline of the bridge, which suggests adequate load transfer from panel to panel by the steel connection plates. Generally, the flexural strain measured in the steel connection plates were smaller in magnitude than those in the FRP, possibly the result of slip occurring between the connection plate and the panels as well as other factors.

Figure 11. Transverse load distribution at mid-span.

The truck positioning induces a maximum moment of 292 ft-kip in the simple span bridge occurring under the middle axle. The maximum moment and the maximum measured deflection induced by the truck positioning was 292 ft-kip and 0.34 in., respectively. The design deflection limit is $L/800$ or 0.59 in. for an H20 loading. An H20 loading induces a calculated maximum moment of 336 ft-kip and a calculated maximum deflection of 0.47 inches. The ratio

of applied test load maximum moment to calculated H20 maximum moment is 87%, which correlated reasonably with the ratio of applied test load maximum deflection to the calculated H20 deflection of 72%. Strain data also correlated reasonably well with the expected strains. For example, the average mid-span strain for load case LC2 was 117 microstrain. The calculated mid-span strain from the test truck was 132 microstrain. Therefore the average measured mid-span strain was within 13% of the anticipated mid-span strain. One potential source of the discrepancy is that the steel splice plate was not taken into account in the calculated mid-span microstrain which has the effect of reducing the strain in the FRP as some of the load is carried by the steel plates. Maximum strain recorded in the steel plate for load case LC2 was 8 microstrain.

Field Implementation

In the spring of 2007, the FRP temporary bypass bridge was installed (see Figure 12a) on a construction project in NE Iowa to allow traffic to flow around a mainline bridge structure that was being replaced. The temporary bridge would have an approximate ADT of 1,000 to 2,000. Timber abutments and backwalls were constructed as specified in the plan documents. However, after placement of the bridge panels it was found that maintaining the specified gap between the abutment backwall and the end of the panels was difficult given the flexibility of the backwall and the pressure from the compacted back fill. After placement of the backfill and the approach roadway sections, the backwalls were found to be partially in contact with the end of the bridge panels raising concern that this could possibly cause premature deterioration of the edge of the panels. Traffic was allowed across the structure and the panel ends were periodically monitored for any signs of wear or damage.

Not long after traffic was allowed on the bridge, Iowa DOT inspectors noticed that the transverse edge at the end of one of the panels was showing signs of damage (see Figure 12b). Investigation of the area found that the elevation of the top of the backwall was approximately 1 in. lower than the elevation of the top of the panel, which caused the leading edge of the panel to be exposed to the full force of oncoming traffic loads. Due to construction time constraints and the need to keep traffic maintained, steel plates were used to span from the approach roadway section to the bridge deck across the abutment joint in an attempt to stop the progression of the deck deterioration (see Figure 12a). In addition, the traffic was reduced from two lanes to one lane.

Shortly after the steel plates were installed, inspection found that the top layer of FRP and the wearing surface had debonded on one of the deck panels over approximately half of the panel surface area (the other panel showed no signs of delamination or deterioration otherwise). In addition, it appeared that water and debris had entered through holes in the top layer of FRP near the lifting lug locations and was resulting in the deterioration of the foam bottles that comprised the core of the panels. It is noteworthy that a load test using strain measurements at the mid-span of the bridge was implemented on the delaminated bridge to assess structural condition. The test results showed that the measured midspan tensile strains were similar to those measured prior to the bridge installation. Even though the tests results indicated no reduction in overall bridge stiffness and adequate lateral load distribution, the bridge was removed from service. The bridge is currently being stored on DOT property on temporary abutments and is being maintained and routinely inspected. After a thorough inspection and evaluation of the damage has been performed, a follow-up load test is likely to evaluate any strength degradation.

(a) Installed FRP Bridge

(b) Deterioration at end of deck panel

Figure 12. Photographs of temporary bypass bridge installation and subsequent deterioration.

Findings

- The initial structural performance of the FRP bridge was satisfactory based on a load test conducted prior to installation. The performance of the bridge was what was expected where the design control is primarily an issue of deflection limitations rather than strength limitations.
- Initial cost of the FRP temporary bridge deck is a potential barrier to replacement of the Iowa DOT steel temporary bridge spans with all FRP spans. Total superstructure cost of the first FRP deck fabricated was \$136 per square foot. The total superstructure cost includes the bridge traffic barrier rail, splice plates and neoprene bearing. The unit cost without the bridge traffic barrier rail or neoprene bearing is \$121 per square foot. Cost to

fabricate new steel temporary detour bridges spans is estimated at \$81,000 per span including the traffic railing for a total superstructure unit cost of \$75 per square foot.

- The delamination of the deck surface at the end of the bridge was 1) likely initially due to vehicle impact from the vertical positioning of the deck at the abutments combined with a lack of edge protection on the deck and 2) subsequently caused by moisture that infiltrated the deck from the surface openings at the end.

OVERALL GENERAL CONCLUSIONS

Based upon structural testing and evaluation, both the FRP panel deck bridge and the FRP detour bridge performed satisfactorily. In both bridges some serviceability issues were observed in the field. Specifically for: 1) the FRP panel deck bridge some degree of delamination/debonding after the first year was observed; however, this initial material deterioration did not significantly affect the structural response, and 2) the FRP detour bridge end details at the bridge approach allowed initiation of deck edge damage from tire impact.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This investigation was conducted by the Bridge Engineering Center at Iowa State University. The authors wish to acknowledge to the Federal Highway Administration, the Iowa Department of Transportation, Highway Division and the Iowa Highway Research Board for the funding to sponsor this research project. Also, they would like to thank the staff of the Bettendorf Public Works Department, especially Public Works Director Wally Mook, for all the assistance provided during this work.

REFERENCES

1. Reising, R. M. W., B. M. Shahrooz, V. J. Hunt, A. R. Newman and A. J. Helmicki. 2004. *Performance comparison on four fiber-reinforced polymer deck panels*. Journal of Composite Structures 2004; 8(3), pp. 265–274.
2. Stiller, W. B., J. Gergely, and R. Rochelle. 2006. *Testing, Analysis, and Evaluation of a GFRP Deck on Steels Girders*. Journal of Bridge Engineering © ASCE. July/August 2006. pp. 394–400.
3. Alampalli, S, J. O'Connor, and A. P. Yannotti, *Design, Fabrication, Construction, and Testing of an FRP Superstructure*, Special Report 134, Transportation Research and Development Bureau, New York State Department of Transportation, December 2000.
4. Alampalli, S, G. Schongar, and H. Greenberg, *In-Service Performance of an FRP Superstructure*, Special Report 141, Transportation Research and Development Bureau, New York State Department of Transportation, March 2004.
5. Wipf, T. J., B. M. Phares, F. W. Klaiber, and U. Deza, *Evaluation of the Bettendorf Bridge, Iowa*, Final Report, Center for Transportation Research and Education, July 2006. <http://www.ctre.iastate.edu/research/reports.cfm>
6. AASHTO. *Standard Specifications for Highway Bridges, Sixteenth Edition*. Washington, DC. American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials. 1996.
7. AASHTO LRFD. *LRFD Bridge Design Specifications*. Washington, DC. American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials.

8. Wipf, T. J., B. M. Phares, D. L. Wood and J. S. Nelson, *Testing and Evaluation of the Iowa DOT FRP Temporary Bypass Bridge*, Final Report, Center for Transportation Research and Education, March 2008. <http://www.ctre.iastate.edu/research/reports.cfm>
9. O'Connor, J. *FRP Decks and Superstructures: Current Practice*. US Department of Transportation, Federal Highway Administration, March 2007
<http://www.fhwa.dot.gov/bridge/frp/deckprac.cfm>
10. Ross, H. E., D. L. Sicking, R.A. Zimmer, and J.D. Michie. *NCHRP Report 350: Recommended Procedures for the Safety Performance and Evaluation of Highway Features*. TRB, National Research Council, Washington, DC. 1993.
11. AASHTO. 2006. *LRFD Bridge Design Specifications with Interim Revisions*. 3rd Edition. American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials, Washington, DC.